

1 **The genes encoded at the Dxz4 locus, DANT1/2, are components of an Xist gene expression**
2 **regulation apparatus that utilizes quantitative control of message quantity of specific genes to**
3 **measure and maintain transcription, globally, within homeostatic range.**

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8 Inclusion of Dxz4 locus transcripts (DANT1 and DANT2) within the homeostatic regulatory system utilizing
9 Xist imprinting thus supports transcriptional homeostasis by regulating Xist activation through control of a
10 locus that controls imprinting control region activation and expression of Xist itself, which is then kept
11 within homeostatic limits, a feature that further constrains Xist activation.

12 The functions important for loss of “physiologic threshold” by maintenance of transcriptional homeostasis
13 (expression change boundaries) during Xist activation or silencing events resulting from DNA damage and
14 other cellular or genomic insults, together demonstrate the existence of a gene expression regulation
15 apparatus that utilizes quantitative control of message quantity of specific genes to measure and maintain
16 transcription, globally, within homeostatic range.